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Hcg4 silencing in acute HCV infection.

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We measured total transcription in the whole blood in humans with Hepatitis C during early acute infection. We report here silencing of the histocompatibility related gene *Hcg4* in the blood during acute HCV infection *in vivo*.

Citations

1. Mamoor, S., The HLA complex non-coding RNA HCG4 is differentially expressed in the blood of patients with coronavirus co-infections. 2020.

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